

JOINT NEWSLETTER

Dear subscribers,

[EU4Advice](#) and [COREnet](#) are continuing their collaboration to strengthen advisory services for Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs) across Europe through the **Local Food Advisors Journey 2026**.

Developed by the two projects, this learning and exchange programme showcases the work of the **European Advisory Network for Short Food Supply Chains (EAN-SFSC)** and actively involves advisors in its development. Advisors are invited not only to take part, but also to contribute their experiences, questions and good practices from across Europe.

Throughout 2026, the Journey will offer **webinars, trainings, practice abstracts, short project videos** and other learning materials to support advisors interested in SFSCs and innovative advisory approaches. **Past advisinars** and related resources will also remain **available**, allowing participants to catch up and continue learning at their own pace.

A central part of the programme is **Advisors Monday**, a monthly one-hour online webinar taking place on the **third Monday of each month at 10:00 CET**. This regular space offers advisors from participating countries the opportunity to exchange knowledge, discuss practical challenges and get inspired by colleagues across Europe.

In this newsletter issue, you will also find the latest updates from the projects, recent events, and useful resources to support your work and stay connected with the SFSC advisory community.

Stay updated and join the Local Food Advisors Journey 2026 to learn, exchange and contribute to the growing European network of SFSC advisors.

ADVISORS' JOURNEY 2026

CORENET **EU4Advice**

**COREnet and EU4Advice
launch the “Local Food
Advisors’ Journey 2026”**

JOIN OUR
NETWORK

[Learn more](#)

The Local Food Advisors Journey 2026, developed by EU4Advice and COREnet, will connect advisors across Europe through webinars, trainings, practice abstracts and videos to exchange knowledge and strengthen short food supply chains.

[Learn more](#)

COREnet Advisors' Corner

A dedicated space for advisors. COREnet offers practical resources, peer learning opportunities, and advisinars designed to share best practices, real-life experiences, and useful tools.

[Learn more](#)

EU4Advice Advisors' Corner

Get all the programme information such as the essentials documents, advisinar videos, presentations, brief project videos and other useful materials.

[Read More](#)

CORENET LATEST NEWS

From panels to field visits: COREnet's Polish European Roadshow tackles the digital future of local food markets

Organised by IsoTech on behalf of COREnet, the two-day event in Kraków brought together researchers, advisors, practitioners and city administrators to explore how digitalisation can strengthen short food supply chains.

[Read More](#)

EU4ADVICE LATEST NEWS

What happens when a European project arrives at Cloughjordan Ecovillage?

Read about the gathering of EU4Advice consortium in Ireland for a Living Lab cross visit hosted at the Cloughjordan Ecovillage, a place where sustainability is a daily practice.

[Read more](#)

Interviews

In this section, we will share a selection of interviews conducted by each project. These conversations offer valuable insights into the experiences, achievements, and perspectives of those working to advance the goals of EU4Advice and COREnet.

COREnet stories - Stronger farms, stronger networks

How peer learning and cooperation are helping local producers face new challenges by Ludovic Josse

[Click Here](#)

COREnet stories - From misunderstood to essential

How research and collaboration are strengthening local food systems across Europe by Yuna Chiffolleau

[Click Here](#)

Sabine van Giesbergen
De Hoge Born Foundation

My suggestion is, definitely go and visit other similar businesses and spend some time working with them. Get as much knowledge as you can and investigate what collaborations are possible.

EU4Advice International Women's Campaign - Roots, Rhythms & Real Work

An interview with Sabine van Giesbergen

[Click Here](#)

EU4Advice International Women's Campaign - Feeding the World

How Nita van Dam is Growing a Healthier and More Sustainable Food System with Nimble

Nita van Dam
Co-founder of Nimble

Nimble sells fresh, seasonal, pre-cut vegetable mixes. We use nature-inclusive and organic vegetables to accelerate farming that prioritizes soil health and allows us to pay farmers fairly.

[Click Here](#)

CORENET LIGHTHOUSE PROJECTS

**STRENGTHENING PEER LEARNING AND ADVISORY
COMPETENCE ACROSS EUROPE'S SHORT FOOD
SUPPLY CHAINS**

Discover what a Lighthouse Project is and become part of the COREnet network

[Read More](#)

EU4ADVICE PRACTICE ABSTRACTS NOW AVAILABLE

A practice abstract is a brief summary that highlights key information, recommendations, or practices that end-users can directly apply in their everyday work.

[Read More](#)

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